

ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Title	Intermediate Data Management Plan
Work package n°	5
Deliverable n°	5.6
Lead beneficiary	ICOS ERIC
Author(s)	Damien Boulanger, Guillaume Brissebrat, Richard Rud, Markus Fiebig, Lynn Hazan, Cathrine Lund Myhre, Ute Karstens, Claudio D'Onofrio, Valérie Thouret, Pawel Wolff, Alex Vermeulen
Deliverable Type	ORDP: Open research data pilot
Dissemination Level	Public
Estimated delivery date	24
Actual delivery date	18 March 2024
Version	1.1
Reviewed by	WP5 task leaders
Accepted by	ATMO-ACCESS Project office
Comments	The initial DMP was created using DMPonline (https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/). This is a slightly updated document based on the initial DMP, that refers for the details to relevant DMPs and documentation of the individual Ris.

Table of Contents

1.	ATMO ACCESS Project DMP.....	3
2.	Data summary.....	4
3.	FAIR data.....	6
3.1.	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:.....	6
3.2.	Making data openly accessible:	7
3.3.	Making data interoperable:	8
3.4.	Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):.....	8
4.	Allocation of resources	9
5.	Data security	10
6.	Ethical aspects.....	10
7.	Other	10

1. ATMO ACCESS Project DMP

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline (<https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>)

Creator: Alex Vermeulen

Affiliation: ICOS ERIC

Funder: European Commission

Template: Horizon 2020 DMP

ORCID iD: 0000-0002-8158-8787

Project abstract:

The ambition of ATMO-ACCESS is to address the needs for developing sustainable solutions based on the principles of open access and to develop guidelines and recommendations for governance, management and funding for efficient and effective access provision suited to distributed atmospheric RIs. This project investigates the most suitable mechanisms that could lead to the sustainable provision of access to atmospheric research infrastructures.

The main objectives of ATMO-ACCESS are:

- to provide coordinated open physical, remote and virtual access to state-of-the-art facilities and services in atmospheric RIs and further enhance their range of products, capabilities and accessibility for a wide range of users, including the private sector.
- to engage facilities and their national stakeholders and direct them towards improved harmonization of access procedures across the different member states, while also exploring modalities by which the use of atmospheric RIs can be further enhanced.
- to explore and test new modalities of access that build on the complementarity and synergies among atmospheric RIs and respond to the evolving needs of users in relation to training, research and technology development, innovation, and data services.
- to identify the most suitable conditions for establishing sustainable access procedures across the EU for distributed atmospheric RIs, involving national and international stakeholders.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004.

ID: 88595

Start date: 01-04-2021

End date: 31-03-2025

DMP last modified: 25-02-2024

Grant number / URL: 101008004 (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101008004>)

2. Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

Specify the origin of the data

State the expected size of the data (if known)

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

In ATMO ACCESS, different Research Infrastructures (RIs) are involved that each represent different communities in atmospheric research. Each of these have activities that generate data according to specific community standards that vary from RI to RI. Work from previous projects like ENVRIplus and ENVRI-FAIR have resulted in significant convergence of the FAIRness of the data handling and data repositories across the RIs. However, because of the different technical requirements and harmonization at the global level for their respective field of research each community still needs to support a set of unique data vocabularies, data types and data formats.

In the ATMO ACCESS project, a lot of data will be generated that is specific to one or more of the RIs, next to more generic and/or common data. RI specific data of course will be curated by the most appropriate RI and stored at the respective data store of that RI. For the data management of this RI specific data the DMP or data lifecycle description of the responsible RI will apply, which should not be duplicated here. In chapter 6 we list the relevant (living) documents from the RIs that describe the data management at the individual RIs.

The users of the Access services of ATMO ACCESS generate data as well. The project offers to host that data through the most applicable RI data center or data centers, in which case the respective RI DMPs apply again. An important condition for all data provided through the ATMO ACCESS project is that the attribution to the project including the Project name and contract number is assured in the metadata.

The focus of this DMP is the generic and common data generated by the project. Curation of the data generated by the (virtual) access setup and managed by the project is part of the homeless data service developed in the project. All data curation there will be following the DMP of the respective RIs that will host the data when this data fits their capabilities. All other

data not fitting the supported data categories will be referred to curation through more general repositories like Zenodo and Pangaea.

Applications for access to research facilities offered in the TNA (Trans National Access) and VA (Virtual Access) sections of the ATMO ACCESS project are open to the scientific community. TNA requests will be evaluated and selected on the basis of scientific excellence but VA is open for web access without prior restrictions, although in the process requests can be rejected because they are out of scope or cannot be accommodated, for example because of a missing relation of the data with one of the participating infrastructures. In the Virtual Access services we offer three services, of which the Homeless Data service is most relevant for the DMP. The Homeless Data service provides curation and publication of relevant data sets from for example measurement campaigns that are produced outside the participating research infrastructures, for example in connected European projects.

The Homeless Data VA supports the community to deliver their data and descriptive metadata according to the FAIR principles as much as possible. Through the services offered in the ATMO ACCESS project for the homeless data, data flows through the RI repositories and follows the FAIR workflows developed there. To ingest and curate the data this requires the users to provide metadata and data according to the metadata and data format standards of the particular RI. The Homeless Data VA therefore first requires the user to provide information through a set of forms at the common entry point so that the VA service can select the RI that presents the best fit with the data, so that greenhouse gas in situ data in principle is hosted by ICOS, vertical profile data by IAGOS and aerosol and reactive gas data by ACTRIS. The data contributor will then further be contacted by the respective RI data manager to further guide the data curation process, that follows the data management plan and procedures of the respective RI, as detailed in the documents listed in chapter 7 of this document.

The Virtual Access services were developed in the first half of the project and became operational since mid 2023. These services deliver mainly time averaged timeseries of atmospheric concentrations of atmospheric composition. These timeseries data sizes are usually in the order of single to maximally hundreds of megabytes for 10–20-year time series, so storage size is not a big issue, as either VA services or the TNA campaigns are relatively short in time. In the case that raw data needs to be stored on for example ceilometer or PTRS data, data volumes can increase to the order of several Gigabytes per campaign, which is well within the range that is manageable. Overall, we expect that the total data volume generated in the ATMO ACCESS project will be maximally several TB, divided over the 3 repositories.

In principal all data generated by the project are open and accessible through open licenses such as CC BY 4, and shared through open repositories such as the repositories from the RI

involved in the project, Zenodo, Pangaea. Data from the TNA campaigns or data generated in the VA services can be part of other research projects and the data generators/owners have the need to publish the data under different licenses or keep part of the data under embargo until the research has been published. All RIs and repositories advised support the possibility of embargo for the data and whenever possible offer as much as possible support for other licenses than the default of the repository.

Software generated specifically for the project will be shared as open source and made available through the GPL v3 or similar open licence model in an open repository like Github.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism.

Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Outline naming conventions used

Outline the approach towards search keyword

Outline the approach for clear versioning

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

Applications for access to research facilities offered in the TNA and VA sections of the ATMO ACCESS project are open to the scientific community and will be evaluated and selected based on scientific excellence. The community is supported to deliver their (meta)data according to the FAIR principles and through the services offered in the project for the homeless data. All data flows through the already FAIR RI repositories and follow the FAIR workflow developed there, as described in the individual RI data management plans and documented workflows. The RIs are continuously improving their data and metadata handling and have made large strides for example in the recently concluded ENVRIFAIR project, to be continued in the new ENVRIHub Next project.

All data and metadata will be published using persistent and unique identifiers such as ePIC Handle and DOI. Final results will be in principle always be published through a Datacite DOI, in most cases of multiple files of different type as a data collection where each individual data object is identified by its own PID.

File naming conventions are irrelevant for FAIR data objects and each community and user can follow their own best practices when this is relevant for data use in the community or project.

Keywords follow the ENVRI-FAIR standard and will use for variable names the CF standard names (<https://cfconventions.org/standard-names.html>), where possible and appropriate. For keywords we recommend the GCMD nomenclature (<https://earthdata.nasa.gov/earth-observation-data/find-data/idn/gcmd-keywords>).

Raw data, if curated by ATMO ACCESS, will not be versioned but always consist of immutable data objects containing the data as generated now, as calculated or measured by the device, datalogger or instrument. Each data processing action in ATMO ACCESS will generate higher level data that is clearly annotated with metadata that provides the provenance information that at least explains, who (persons, affiliation), how (software, version), with which parameters (document or machine readable parameter file) and following which protocol (document, script or other machine readable workflow), all identified with persistent and unique identifiers and provided as data object with the dataset or linked through by open access. Each consecutive processing in the chain will deliver a next version of the dataset, the incremental version number will be part of the provenance metadata and consist of an indicator of major version changes followed by an indicator of minor changes, in the format of integer numbers separated by a decimal dot, such as for example "2.5".

Data providers that generate data in the TNA activities are encouraged to follow the principles described here but complete following of these guidelines cannot be guaranteed, unless they submit as recommended through the ATMO ACCESS VA Homeless Data services. It might very well be the case that users that will make use of the TNA or VA homeless data portal follow their own curation and intermediate storage and data processing and only want to store and make accessible final quality-controlled data products through the project. In that case they can make use of the homeless data portal, and the project ensures that the (meta)data follows the respective FAIR data handling of the responsible RI data repository for that part.

In that case, metadata will follow the ENVRI-FAIR recommendations of the respective community and at least follow either Dublin Core, ISO19115 or DCAT AP v2.

3.2. Making data openly accessible:

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

Specify how the data will be made available

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

In principle all data and software generated by the project will be open and be accessible through open licenses such as CC BY 4 and GPL 3.0 and shared through open repositories such as the RI repositories, Zenodo, Pangaea and Github.

Data from the TNA campaigns or data generated in the VA services can be part of other research projects and the data generators/owners will also have the need to publish the data under different licenses or keep part of the data under embargo until the research has been published. All RIs and repositories advised will support the possibility of embargo for the data and whenever possible offer support for other licenses than the default of the repository.

All data access through the RI and advised repositories already follow the FAIR principles and provide data through open and public protocols. Through the data curation of homeless data service, we make sure that data formats are following the community open standards, in this case mostly NASA-AMES, ASCII and CF compliant netcdf and hdf.

3.3. Making data interoperable:

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Through the data curation of homeless data service, we make sure that data formats are following the community open standards, in this case mostly NASA-AMES, ASCII and CF compliant netcdf and hdf.

Each data processing action in ATMO ACCESS generates higher level data that is clearly annotated with metadata that provides the provenance information that at least explains, who (persons, affiliation), how (software, version), with which parameters (document or machine readable parameter file) and following which protocol (document, script or other machine readable workflow), all identified with persistent and unique identifiers and provided as data object with the dataset or linked through by open access.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Describe data quality assurance processes

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

In principle, all data and software generated by the project will be open and be accessible through open licenses such as CC BY 4 and GPL 3.0, shared through open repositories such as the RI repositories, Zenodo, Pangaea and Github.

Data from the TNA campaigns or data generated in the VA services can be part of other research projects and the data generators/owners will also have the need to publish the data under different licenses or keep part of the data under embargo until the research has been published. All RIs and repositories advised will support the possibility of embargo for the data and whenever possible offer support for other licenses than the default of the repository.

The data will be kept for as long as the foreseen life-time of the RIs' and external repositories. All of these repositories have a long-term perspective of at least 5 years from now and in most case an even longer time span (>20 years), with all providing contingency procedure to preserve the data outside the repository in the case the repository has to be terminated.

4. Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

The costs of the FAIR provision of data and metadata is provided from the operational funding of the RIs. The marginal costs of the additional storage of (meta)data from this project is provided by this project, that allows to develop the Virtual Access Services and support the operation of these during the second half of the project. Additional support for example of use of EOSC services like the B2SAFE replication of data is provided by other projects like EOSC OSCARS and ENVRI Hub Next.

The data management responsibilities are clearly defined in the project Description of Action and will be further detailed during the development of the services through for example the deliverables D5.1 and D5.3. Further details are described in the documents listed in section 2.6.

5. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

All RIs provide secure storage of the submitted data and metadata and have in place redundancy of storage, with regular additional backups to restore the state of the repository in case of failures. In general, the research data generated in this project is not sensitive or privacy relevant data.

6. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

Ethics are in general not applicable on the research data generated in this field of research. All personal data will be processed according to the European GDPR regulation and the applicable national laws for the different institutes.

7. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

ICOS data management practices are described in:

- [ICOS Data Policy](#)
- [ICOS Data Lifecycle Document](#)
- Details on m2m metadata management: <https://github.com/ICOS-Carbon-Portal/meta>
- Details on m2m data submission and access: <https://github.com/ICOS-Carbon-Portal/data>

ACTRIS data management practices are described in: [ACTRIS DMP](#)

- NILU/EBAS data management practices are described in: <https://ebas-submit.nilu.no>

IAGOS data management data practices are described in: [IAGOS Data Management Plan](#)

